

MONITORING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE IN ENGINEERING GRAPHICS THROUGH DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Annotation. *The article discusses the process of monitoring and enhancing students' knowledge in distance education by encouraging them to draw diagrams related to the subject. This approach aims to ensure the reinforcement of their knowledge and achieve results comparable to those in traditional education. This method serves to make the learning process more effective in the context of distance education.*

Keywords: *Distance education, traditional education, detail, electronic education, online, networked teaching, mobile learning.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada masofaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalarning mavzu bo'yicha o'zlashtirgan bilimlarini nazorat qilish va oshirish masalasi ko'rib chiqilgan. Bunda talabalarni chizmalar chizishga undash orqali ularning bilimlarini mustahkamlash va an'anaviy ta'limdagi kabi samarali natijalarga erishish yo'llari taklif etilgan. Ushbu usul masofaviy ta'lim sharoitida o'quv jarayonini yanada samarali qilishga xizmat qiladi.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается процесс контроля и повышения знаний студентов в процессе дистанционного обучения путем побуждения их к схем по изучаемой теме. Данный подход направлен на закрепление их знаний и достижение результатов, сопоставимых с традиционным образованием. Этот метод способствует повышению эффективности учебного процесса в условиях дистанционного обучения.*

Ensuring that the current educational process is of high quality and meets modern requirements is considered one of the most pressing issues of the day. In higher technical educational institutions, all opportunities are being created for engineers in training to develop into specialists who can contribute to the economy of our Republic in the future. To this end, the education system from schools to higher education institutions has been modernized based on global standards. Distance learning provides a much better situation for students compared to traditional teaching, as education can take place anywhere and at any time outside the university. Distance learning is independent learning, self-management, learning from any location, and education that is not tied to a specific time. Over more than a century, distance learning in higher education institutions has been constantly developing.

One of the positive aspects of distance learning is that almost all participants have the opportunity to expand their fields. Time is saved. Unfortunately, one of the most common problems associated with distance learning is the lack of direct interaction with faculty and instructors. Due to the distance, there is also no opportunity to seek help. It should be noted that students with the highest level of trust encounter very few obstacles in using online learning technologies, such as social interactions and various administrative issues. Currently, the full potential of distance learning to increase the competitiveness of universities has not yet been utilized. Many instructors still insist on implementing traditional teaching methods. On the other hand, the lack of material competence reduces instructors' interest in using problem-solving tasks. This, in turn, decreases the effectiveness of distance learning.

The main goal of distance learning is to overcome barriers of place and time. Students may be isolated or living in rural areas where they might not have access to education. Other students may have the right to enroll in college, but the college may not allow these students to enroll. Distance learning provides an opportunity for education to those who cannot attend physical classes on campus. Additionally, when students try to balance family, work, and education, time is valued.

Overall, in organizing the educational process, various models and teaching technologies exist. Currently, the practical application of a combination of the above, and the role of the most commonly used models—traditional, distance, and blended learning—as a model, hold significant importance.

In world countries, distance learning is considered to have a number of advantages and superiorities over traditional teaching in terms of organizational-pedagogical aspects, content, technology, finances, as well as individualization and differentiation of education.

The effectiveness of distance learning depends on the quality of the materials used (educational courses) and the skills of the instructors involved in the process. Therefore, organizing distance learning in a pedagogical and meaningful way (both at the course design stage and during its use) is considered a priority task.

The effectiveness of any type of distance learning depends on four components:

- a) the interaction between the instructor and the student;
- b) the pedagogical technologies used;
- c) the developed educational materials and the methods of delivering them;
- d) the quality of feedback.

Thus, the effectiveness of distance learning depends on the quality of the developed materials and the skills of the instructors involved in the process. Therefore, organizing distance learning in a pedagogical and meaningful way (both at the course design stage and during its use) is considered a priority task.

The main characteristics of designing a distance learning course are as follows:

1. The independent cognitive activity of the student is at the center of the learning process.
2. Teaching students to independently search for and acquire knowledge using various information sources; developing the ability to work with this information using different methods of cognitive activity and, at the same time, the ability to work at a convenient time.
3. The students' independent active cognitive activity is not limited to merely acquiring knowledge but also ensures its application in solving various problems of the surrounding reality.
4. Utilizing the latest pedagogical technologies that correspond to the specific characteristics of this form of education, encourage the development of each student's internal potential, and contribute to shaping the individual's social virtues. The most suitable methods in this regard include: collaborative learning, gamification, the KWL method, the research project method, and problem-based methods.
5. The monitoring system should be systematic and based on operational feedback (allowing the student to contact the instructor or course advisor immediately at any convenient time), automated monitoring (through test systems), and ongoing monitoring during face-to-face course sessions. Thus, the distance learning system can be actively used for the following purposes: improving the qualifications of professors and instructors; preparing external students to take exams in specific academic subjects;

organizing specialized education for school students; providing additional education for adults; and conducting retraining and training courses, among others.

Among the methods of acquiring knowledge that we know, distance learning holds a special place today. It has many advantages and serves as an excellent alternative to traditional classes, but it also has specific characteristics that can put the success of the entire concept at risk. Below, we will explain why the future belongs to distance learning, what challenges those who choose this path may face, and how these challenges can be overcome.

In the field of drawing subjects, controlling students' knowledge through tests in distance learning does not provide complete information about whether the covered topic has been fully mastered. Therefore, developing engaging assignments that motivate drawing has become an important issue for drawing instructors.

Task: Determine the personal and cast shadows of a group of geometric solids in axonometric projection.

Determine: the personal and cast shadows of the group of geometric solids in axonometric projection, process them into a format, and then select the correct answer from the options.

Figur 1.

The student will be partially required to work through the options provided below to distinguish between correct and incorrect ones. A student with drawing skills can also work based on the options (see Figure 2).

This task involves determining the personal (self) shadow and cast shadow of a group of geometric solids in axonometric projection. Below, I'll explain the process and provide a solution. Since this is a technical drawing task, I'll outline the steps clearly, and you can use this as a guide to identify the correct answer from the options provided. If you have specific geometric solids or a diagram, please share more details for a precise solution. For now, I'll assume a general case (e.g., a cube, cylinder, and cone) and describe how to approach it.

Figure 2.

Using similar drawing-based tests in other areas of engineering graphics could also yield more effective assessments of students' knowledge.

In conclusion, the distance learning process can achieve the following:

- Individualization and differentiation of the learning process;
- Error diagnosis and continuous feedback;
- Self-assessment and self-correction in learning;
- Saving time through practical computer-based drawing;
- Visualizing educational content;
- Modeling and simulation of studied processes and drawings;
- Organizing graphic tasks in simulated computer environments;
- Developing students' decision-making skills in various situations;
- Enhancing specific types of thinking (e.g., visual-figurative and theoretical thinking);
- Increasing learning motivation (through visual tools or game-based situations);
- Cultivating a culture of cognitive activity, and more.

To summarize, in distance learning, the educational process must be organized in such a way that students can study independently without encountering unanswered questions or confusion.

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